

Designing An Innovation Model For Ips Learning

Ade Isma Nurfata¹, Asgipen Debatara², Mugniar Handayani³,
Candri Ratna Palupi⁵, Yayan Sudrajat⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Indraprasta PGRI University

Correspondence Email : amarsptn@gmail.com

Article History: Submitted: 2023.05.28 Revised: 2023.05.29 Accepted: 2022.06.07 Published: 2023.06.30

ABSTRACT

It is anticipated that the low level of learning will tend to decrease if faced with very rapid changes in society. This relates to the very rapid use of science and technology in various aspects. Strategy based on paradigm, that there are two forces that influence the demands and challenges of education. First, education is faced with the challenge of playing a role in strengthening the value system, in enhancing the quality of faith and devotion. Second, education is faced with paradigmatic demands to play education in mastering science and technology. This challenge arises and demands to be faced simultaneously, and demands a strategic answer by integrating policy and culture within the framework of improving the quality of Indonesian people to welcome 2020 through improving the quality of education. This challenge, which is related to innovation in the learning process, clearly demands a conceptual direction regarding innovation in the learning process, so that students have the ability to empower the potential of faith and devotion to God Almighty as a spiritual force and how learning can effectively empower potential in mastering science and technology. In essence, social studies learning innovation is an effort to continuously improve the quality of the educational process, to meet the development of society's demands for education. In this way, innovation in social studies learning will be effective, when indicated by the results of evaluation and research in the field of social studies learning. Learning can be done in joint study groups, which emphasizes group learning. So far, it has been felt that it has not been deliberately developed in the learning process, therefore it is a challenge and demand for learning innovation. If done, it will be able to overcome the weaknesses of learning that has been carried out in the field.

Keywords: Innovation, Learning, Social Sciences

INTRODUCTION

Innovation is an idea, idea, practice or object/object that is recognized and accepted as something new by a person or group for adoption. Therefore, innovation is basically brilliant thinking which are characterized by new things or in the form of certain practices or in the form of products resulting from thought and technological processes applied through certain stages which are believed to be intended to solve problems that arise and improve certain conditions or certain processes that occur in society (Ahira, 2011:33). Meanwhile, according to Kusmana (2010: 4) innovation is making changes or introducing something new. From the opinion above, it can be concluded that innovation is a process that produces new products or new ideas with the aim of improving existing ones so that they are better than previous conditions or situations thereby increasing efficiency, relevance, quality and effectiveness.

Educational innovation according to Asrori (2011:15) is innovation in the field of education to solve problems in education. Educational innovation includes matters related to the components of the education system, both in a narrow sense at the level of educational institutions and in a broader sense in the national education system. So it can be said that curriculum innovation is something that can occur within the scope of education.

In a scope that is more focused on learning, educators develop more learning innovations in their practice in schools. According to Hasbullah, (2001:44), learning innovation is a new effort in the learning

process, using various methods, approaches, facilities and an atmosphere that supports the achievement of learning goals. Based on this thinking, educators are expected to design and create learning innovations in order to create fun and meaningful learning.

Specifically, learning media is a form of learning innovation that is easy to develop and is an indicator of educator creativity. The results of the application and media products are very visible to the eye. In this media it will be seen whether an educator is able to be creative or not.

The characteristics of learning media innovation contain elements of original, specific, unique, creative, systematic, applicable, inspiring, useful, interesting, IT and art based (Aris Riyadi, 2020: 37). The authenticity of the results of media creation. The learning carried out by educators is the main marker of the level of learning media innovation. If the media is written in the form of a written work, its authenticity can be tested using similarity and sitacy tests. Learning media should be specific, that is, the work created must be specifically applied in the learning process. Learning media is unique in that it has its own special values and has never existed before. Meanwhile, learning media is characterized by creativity, namely that the media contains elements of novelty or improves an existing form into a new form.

Learning media needs to be described systematically regarding guidelines for using media in the learning process. Learning media should be applicable, that is, easy to use and develop wherever they are and cheap and easy to manufacture. The usefulness of the media needs to be taken into account when learning media is created. Attractive and pleasant physical form also needs to be paid attention to so that when using media students are more interested. Apart from being interesting and useful in the digitalization era of the industrial revolution 4.0, learning media needs to be developed based on information and communication technology. However, media that relies on technological sophistication alone is not enough. Many media that are purely technology-based actually become dry and artificial.

For this reason, the element of art is a solution for developing innovative learning media. The combination of elements of information communication technology and elements of art will produce media that is not only updated but also contains elements of interest and fun. If learning media has been successfully created, it will be even greater when the learning media becomes the inspiration for the creation of the next learning media. Many forms of media are able to inspire the emergence of other media, for example historical wayang media. This media inspired the emergence of new media such as fable wayang media, finger puppet media and so on.

The current phenomenon in schools shows that the teaching and learning process in schools is generally considered uninteresting, so that students are less interested in taking these subjects, as stated by Velarasi (2004: 7). Many educators convey their learning only through lectures or questions and answers or taking notes on the blackboard. Various learning scenarios cannot be carried out due to time constraints, the choice of unsuitable learning models and media and the limited ability of educators to implement them. The practice of applying media should be fun. The process of creating and applying media in learning is what is called learning media innovation.

There are many examples of learning media innovation, either by modifying existing learning media or creating new learning media that did not previously exist. Whether it is in the form of conventional or IT-based, or even combining IT and conventional. Conventional learning media innovations include: card media, doll media, wayang media, snakes and ladders media, origami media and so on. Meanwhile, IT-based learning media innovations can be developed from multimedia. Multimedia is a combination of various kinds of learning media, namely combining audio, visual, audio-visual media, realia, internet, cellphones and so on. Even multimedia using cellphones, computers, the internet and the like is an effective, interactive and wide-reaching learning medium. Seeing the development of students in the current era, learning media needs to integrate technology and information in an interactive learning process. Currently, there are many IT-based interactive learning media that can be used in the learning process, for example Kahoot, Quizizz, Quipper, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality and the like. The more creative and innovative an educator is, the more diverse the creation of new learning media will be.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is library research (Ramadani and Herdi 2021). Library research is an activity related to methods of collecting library materials, reading and taking notes, and managing research materials. Meanwhile, (Nuryono 2020) literature study is a method that can be used in research by reading and studying things related to the object to be researched. The data collection method, namely the documentation method according to (Ramadani and Herdi 2021), is a consolidation of data collection

methods obtained from various literature into one document that is used to answer the problem formulation. (Yaniawati 2020) explains the literature research procedure, namely. choosing a topic, researching information, determining research objectives, collecting sources of information, reading sources of information, making research notes, processing research notes, preparing reports. The source of information is bibliographic or comes from different literature, including books, magazines, newspapers, personal documents, etc. The library research instrument is the researcher himself (human instrument). Researchers act as data collectors, analysts, interpreters, planners, implementers and finally reporters of research results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Designing Innovative Learning Media

In the world of education, learning media has an important role in teaching and learning activities. Learning media itself has the aim of making the teaching and learning process more effective and easier to implement. But in reality, learning media is often neglected due to limited time to make teaching preparations, difficulty finding the right media, and unavailability of funds. So that the learning process is easy and efficient, educators must choose media that is relevant to the learning objectives to be achieved. There are many types of learning media innovations that can actually be applied in teaching and learning activities.

The first step that educators must take in designing learning media is to analyze media needs so that learning objectives can be achieved well. Educators will start by analyzing learning media needs that are in accordance with KI, KD, GPA and student characteristics. One format that can be used to analyze learning media needs is the format for analyzing learning media needs in the current semester or also in the current year. The function of this format is so that the media can be properly inventoried or mapped and adjusted to the basic competencies or existing themes. From here it will become a reference for including forms of media in the implementation of learning.

The second step is to determine which media will be selected based on the results of the analysis they have carried out. The selected media can be in the form of existing media, all you have to do is use it or media that doesn't yet exist and must be created first. Homemade media is what makes learning media innovation possible. If media mapping is carried out neatly in the distribution of time allocation, then an educator can prepare the creation of media well in advance of the use of the media. The following is an example of a needs analysis format as a basis for determining what learning media should be created or used.

The third step is to design learning media innovations. When The media has been mapped in one semester, so educators just have to decide which learning media to create. The selected media will be designed as learning media. The design contains the name of the selected media, the form of the design/sketch of the media, the materials needed to make the media, the steps for making the media and a description of the application of the media in learning.

The fourth step is to start creating learning media. Making learning media should be done long before the learning is implemented. So this is the importance of analyzing and designing learning media. With the results of the analysis and design form, an educator will know what media should be created and what steps should be taken. Creation can be done one semester before the semester starts. Production can also collaborate with educators in other subjects. For example, educators who are competent with computers and have high artistic abilities. This will create an interesting learning media.

The fifth step is to apply media to the learning process both in class and outside of class. This application is very closely related to the methods used in the learning process. So the RPP also states what media will be used in the learning. After everything has been done, the fifth step is to evaluate the usefulness of the learning media. The effectiveness of a learning media will not be known if there has not been a trial or evaluation of the usefulness of the media. There are many

ways that can be used to test learning media, both through research and studying the media works created.

The following is an example of a learning media innovation design format for the even semester IX middle school social studies subject. The basic competency taken is 3.4 Analyzing the chronology, changes and continuity of space (geographical, political, economic, educational, social, cultural) from the beginning of independence to the beginning of reform. The scope of the material selected or the theme is about the Proclamation Event.

FORMAT RANCANGAN INOVASI MEDIA PEMBELAJARAN

Sekolah/Mapel : SMPN./IPS
 Kelas/Semester : IX/Genap
 Kompetensi Dasar: 3.4 Menganalisis kronologi, perubahan dan kesinambungan ruang dari awal kemerdekaan sampai awal reformasi
 Tema : Peristiwa Proklamasi
 Media Terpilih : Wayang Sejarah
 Rancangan/sketsa Media:

Bahan yang di perlukan : Kertas duplex, Cat, Stereform, Gambar wajah pahlawan, Benner, Bambu, Musik perjuangan, Narasi peristiwa.

Langkah Pembuatan : 1. Membuat narasi kronologis peristiwa Proklamasi
 2. Menginventaris tokoh tokoh yang berperan Proklamasi
 3. Membuat wajah tokoh proklamasi dari internet
 4. Wajah ditempelkan pada badan wayang
 5. Dst...

Penerapan dalam Pembelajaran:
 1. Wayang sejarah digunakan untuk memfrakmenkan kronologis peristiwa proklamasi.
 2. Peserta didik menyusun kronologis peristiwa Proklamasi dengan bahasanya sendiri
 3. Peserta didik memainkan wayang sejarah tentang peristiwa Proklamasi dengan bahasanya sendiri
 4. Kelompok lain menanggapi tampilan
 5. Dst.....

FORMAT RANCANGAN INOVASI MEDIA PEMBELAJARAN

Sekolah/Mapel : SMP/MTs / IPS
 Kelas/Semester : XI/Genap
 Kompetensi Dasar : 3.4 Menganalisis kronologis perubahan dan kesinambungan ruang dari awal kemerdekaan sampai awal reformasi
 Tema : Peristiwa Proklamasi
 Media Terpilih : Lukis Pasir Sejarah
 Rancangan/sketsa Media:

Bahan yang di perlukan: Stereform. Camera. Tiang penyangga kamera. Laptop. LCD. Kaca. Lampu. Kabel. Stop kontak. Kertas transparan. Kertas plano. Pasir sungai. Narasi peristiwa. Musik perjuangan.

Langkah Pembuatan : 1. Membuat kotak lukis pasir
 2. Menyambungkan kotak dengan kamera
 3. Menyambungkan kamera dengan LCD
 4. Melukis pasir sejarah
 5. Dst...

Penerapan dalam Pembelajaran:
 1. Lukis pasir sejarah digunakan untuk menggambarkan kronologis peristiwa proklamasi.
 2. Peserta didik menyusun kronologis peristiwa proklamasi dengan bahasanya sendiri
 3. Peserta didik menunagkan dalam lukisan pasir sejarah
 4. Kelompok lain menanggapi
 5. Dst.....

The two examples of learning media design formats above are just examples of many alternative formats that can be created to make it easier to design an innovative learning media by a social studies educator. The creation of an innovative learning media cannot be separated from inspiration. Inspiration can appear anywhere, at any time and from any source. An inspiration can be sparked from intrinsic and extrinsic elements. The intrinsic element comes from within an educator. For example, an educator creates new learning media because it is a need that requires them to create learning media because their school does not have or lack the required media. Extrinsic elements are elements from outside an educator. For example, innovation in learning media for social studies subjects can be obtained from observations of other people's innovative learning media works, then processed into a learning media work in a new form.

So the media is inspired by other people's media. If you copy someone else's work exactly then you are just copying without any innovation or new creation. As insa source of inspiration for the emergence of a learning media innovation complete with a link to the learning media demonstration.

- a. Live laboratory media for head lice metamorphosis process
- b. The layered media forms the contours of the earth's surface for tsunamis
- c. Public cemetery media for writing supernatural poetry
- d. Bamboo cumpring hygrometer media for air humidity
- e. Instructional computer media for the blind
- f. Historical lantern media
- g. Fan magic circulation media
- h. Cartoon or caricature media

Interactive poster and diorama media, media demonstration link is at:

<https://youtu.be/cmHLTirOIWE>

Video scribe media using the Jokovi technique, the media demonstration link is at the address:

- a. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PSDYbxAacoM&t=1s>
- b. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8s5IvJ97qs&list=LLqkAL0ub5Qiusb1lmDf1uPA&index=15>

Historical sand painting media, media demonstration link is at the address:

<https://youtu.be/kQNfDww1vQE>

Media for wayang historical figures, the link to the media demonstration is at the address:

- a. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XIIfCWPAE>
- b. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=410fVmFVy5k>

The social studies learning model has its own characteristics, namely emphasizing the individual's relationship with other people or with society, so that the learning model in this category is more focused on increasing the individual's ability to relate to other people, be involved in the democratic process, or be able to collaborate productively. The social studies learning models are as follows:

Concept Achievement Model

The model for achieving this concept was developed by Jerome S. Bruner, Jacqueline Goodrow and George Agustin based on the results of their studies on human thinking. This model is deliberately designed to help students learn concepts that can be used to organize them so that it can make it easier for students to learn these concepts efficiently.

Regarding the meaning of concept, according to Sapriya concept is an abstract concept that connects people with groups of things, events, or thoughts.¹ The birth of the concept was due to awareness of the class attributes shown by the symbol.

From this opinion, the material in a lesson is certainly material that is facts, concepts and generalizations. Where in teaching concept material, of course the teacher must pay attention to aspects related to teaching concept material, such as how to convey the concept. Students' skills in understanding the material are very necessary because it influences student learning outcomes and students' mastery of concepts.

Based on the opinion above, it can be concluded that by improving concept mastery it is hoped that students can easily understand social studies concepts which can also be applied by students in student life. This will also make social studies subjects attract students' attention because learning social studies does not only consist of memorizing from books, but students work together in groups directly to solve social problems that are being faced in their environment.

Inductive thinking model(Induktive Thinking)

The inductive thinking model is a learning model that aims to encourage students to find and organize information so that students can be active and gain meaningful learning experiences so that the learning outcomes obtained by students will improve and last a long time. Meanwhile, the teacher's role in the inductive thinking learning model is to supervise students' processes in searching for information/concepts, guide students through relevant questions and create learning tools that enable students to carry out cognitive and psychomotor tasks in learning appropriately.²

So it can be concluded that this inductive thinking model encourages students to find and organize existing information and makes students able to explore various ways that can make students skilled in responding to and organizing information. So the inductive thinking model is aimed at building cognitive mentality, therefore it is very suitable for developing thinking abilities, and this strategy really requires a lot of information that must be explored by students. And the advantage of this model is that even though it is very suitable for social studies lessons, it can also be used in various other subjects.

Group Investigation Model(Group Investigation

Group Investigation Learning Method (PIK) to improve social skills based on Vygotsky's sociocultural theory about social learning, Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and Scaffolding. This theory views that every individual can achieve abilities potential after receiving assistance from other individuals through an interactive learning process in a social context.

This theory views the importance of social interaction in the learning process in order to be able to achieve one's potential abilities. Because of the importance of interaction in learning, students need to have the ability to interact effectively and harmoniously.³ So the group investigation model is a learning model in which learning activities are carried out by students taking part in the learning process together in group form and are well structured, this is done to solve problems.

The group investigation learning model is a model that can combine learning strategies with the dynamics of the democratic process and the academic process in the form of research. This research takes the form of a challenge to a problem, namely knowledge obtained from research. So it can be concluded that the group investigation model is a cooperative learning strategy which is seen as the most complex and most difficult model to implement in learning because this model involves students from planning, both in determining topics and ways to study them through investigation and emphasizes student participation and activities to Search for the lesson material (information) to be studied yourself through available materials, for example from textbooks or students can search via the internet. This model requires students to have good communication skills and group process skills.

Memorization Model

This model was developed by Pressley and Levin. Memorization is a model used to memorize information. Teachers can use the memorization model to guide the delivery of material which aims to ensure that students can easily capture and remember new information, because this memorization model is directed at developing students' ability to absorb and integrate information so that students can remember the information they have received and can recall it later. required.⁴

The memorization model is a learning model that uses memory to improve memory abilities. The memorization model relates to how the brain works. There are three elements in the brain's actions, namely receiving impressions, storing them and producing them. Each individual has different brain abilities, as well as memory, so the learning outcomes obtained are also different. Therefore, studying repeatedly can help strengthen memory.

For the memorization model, it can be understood that this learning model is directed at developing students' abilities to absorb and integrate information so that students can remember the information they have received and can repeat it when necessary.

Role Playing Model

Role playing learning model(role playing) is a social learning model, namely a learning model that assigns students to play a character in material or an event expressed in the form of a simple story. Role playing learning model(role playing) pioneered by George Shaftel with the assumption that role playing can encourage students to express feelings and lead to awareness through spontaneous involvement accompanied by analysis of real life problem situations.

According to the Djamarah model role playing (role playing) can be said to be the same as sociodrama, which basically dramatizes behavior in relation to social problems. In principle, role playing is learning to present roles that exist in the real world into a role performance in the classroom, which is then used as reflection material so that participants provide an assessment of the learning that has been carried out and then provide suggestions/alternative opinions for role development. -the role. Several advantages of implementing the role-playing learning model(role playing) according to Djamarah, namely:

a. Students train themselves to rehearse, understand and remember the content of the material

- to be dramatized.
- b. Students will be trained to take initiative and be creative.
- c. The talents found in students can be nurtured so that it is possible for drama arts to emerge from school.
- d. Cooperation between players can be grown and nurtured as well as possible.

It is Students acquire the habit of accepting and sharing responsibility with each other. Based on some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that the model role playing is a learning model by assigning students to act out a character in material or an event expressed in the form of a simple story that has been designed by the teacher.

Jurisprudential Review Model

According to Hamzah B. Uno, "The jurisprudential study learning model can train students to be sensitive to social problems, take a position (attitude) towards these problems, and defend this attitude with relevant and valid arguments."⁶ They are required to formulate the issue as a community policy question and analyze alternative positions.

From this statement, it can be concluded that the jurisprudence study learning model is a learning model by conducting discussions or debates between students to discuss a given problem, where each student has the right to express their own opinion and defend that opinion with relevant and valid arguments.

Jurisprudence Study learning model (Juris Prudenstial Inquiry) which was pioneered by Donal Oliver and James P. Shaver, is based on an understanding of society where each person has different views and priorities from each other, and their social values confront each other. Solving complex and controversial problems within the context of productive social order requires citizens who are able to talk to each other and negotiate that existence.

Jurisprudential Analysis Model (Juris Prudenstial Inquiry) is a learning model to help students be able to think systematically about origins in society, especially in the educational environment. The benefit of the inquiry jurisprudence study learning model is to train students to be sensitive to social problems, so that they can take a stance on the problems they face, and defend that stance with relevant and valid arguments.

The jurisprudential study learning model is also useful for training students to accept and respect attitudes towards other people despite contradicting himself and acknowledging the truth of the attitude taken by others towards a certain social issue.

It can be concluded that in this jurisprudential study learning model, students are asked to express a problem based on their arguments after obtaining information, where after expressing their arguments, students listen and listen to other people's opinions and can appreciate the opinions that have been expressed by other students.

Social Inquiry Model

Sanjaya stated that, in the inquiry approach, learning becomes more child-centered, the learning process through inquiry can form and develop students' self-concept, the level of hope increases, the inquiry approach can develop talents, the inquiry approach can prevent students from learning by rote. , and inquiry approaches give students time to assimilate and accommodate information. The inquiry method is one of the teaching methods, the term discovery method or inquiry is defined as a procedure that involves learning individually, manipulating objects or arranging or conditioning an object, and other experimentation by students before a generalization or conclusion is made.

CONCLUSION

The learning media innovations above are only a small part of the many media that can be developed in the educational environment. Creativity and new ideas by adjusting the availability of materials, local wisdom and competency goals to be achieved will become an innovation in learning media. Often creating

new learning media will be a "sparker" for educators' creativity. Nowadays, more and more educators are required to continue to be creative and develop innovation in learning. Whatever is around us, if educators are willing to be creative and innovative, it will become a useful learning medium in fixing existing problems in the educational environment. For this reason, educators throughout Indonesia are encouraged to continue to innovate and be creative without stopping.

Learning predicates that are still boring and uninteresting to students will turn into fun learning with an innovative learning media. Educators who used to be the "scourge" feared by students, are now educators whose presence is always hoped for and awaited.

REFERENCES

- Aunurrahman.2009.Learning and Learning. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- A Wicaksono, Winahyu.Application of the Inductive Thinking Model with Graphic Media to Improve Social Studies Learning Outcomes for Class III Students, Negeri 04 Ngringo,Kebumen PGSD Education Journal, Volume 4, No. 5.1.
- B. Uno, Hamzah. 2007.Learning model. Jakarta: Pustaka Setia.
- B. Uno, Hamzah. 2012.Learning Model (Creating a Creative and Effective Teaching and Learning Process). Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- Jarolimiek, John. 1986.Social Studies in Elementary Education. New York: Macmillan. Nugroho, Riant. 2008.Indonesian Education: Hope, Vision and Strategy, Yogyakarta : Student Library.
- Sanjaya, Vienna. 2006.Learning Strategy, Oriented to Educational Process Standards. Jakarta: Prenada Media Group.
- Sapriya. 2012.Social Sciences Education Concepts and Learning. Bandung: PT Teen Rosdakarya.
- Sardinia. 2017.Social studies education in elementary school. Tangerang: CV TitipanExpress Indonesia.
- Suprihatiningrum, Jamil. 2012.Learning strategies. Yogyakarta : Ar-Ruz Media.
- Tarigan, Arleni. 2016.Application of the Role Playing Learning Model to Improve Social Studies Learning Outcomes for Class III Students at SD Negeri 013 Lubuk Kembang Sari, UKUI District. Primary Journal PGSD Study Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Riau University. Volume 5 No.3.
- Trianto. 2009.Designing Innovative-Progressive Learning Models. Jakarta : Kencana.
- Wasmana.2016.Group Investigation Learning Method (PIK) to improve the social skills of elementary school students. Indonesian education university. Downloaded on November 6, 2019 on http://repository.upi.edu/25209/11/T_PP_1402063_Appendix2.pdf
- Yusnaldi, Eka. 2019.New Portrait of Social Studies Learning. Medan : Perdana Publishing.